

Hybrid Steel-to-Composite Joint Behavior Under Tensile Loading

Sarah E. Mouring, Ph.D., P.E.

Department of Naval Architecture and Ocean Engineering
United States Naval Academy
Annapolis, USA

Luke Louca, Ph.D., and Reuben Brambleby, M.Sc.

Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering
Imperial College London
London, UK

Abstract—Hybrid steel-to-composite joints are being used more commonly for load bearing applications. However, these hybrid joints usually entail geometry and material discontinuities which can induce stiffness mismatch and cause local stress concentrations. The shock impedance mismatch caused by the different wave propagation characteristics can also be crucial to the structural response of the hybrid joints under impulsive loads. Recent research at Imperial College London (ICL) and the U.S. Naval Academy (USNA) has focused on characterizing the behavior and ultimate load capacity of hybrid steel-to-composite joints with different configurations under various loading conditions. This paper presents results from tensile strength testing of steel-to-composite double lap joints, comparing pseudo-static strength with dynamic strength and comparing joints that exploit perforated steel plates with those manufactured with non-perforated steel plates. An intentional manufacturing flaw also was incorporated into half of the joints, both perforated and non-perforated joints, in order to assess the effect of this flaw type on joint strength. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) results are compared to experimental results for both perforated and non-perforated joints.

Keywords—composite; metal; hybrid; joint.

I. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are being more widely used as primary structural members. This is due to the high demand of advanced naval vessels with enhanced performance in terms of damage tolerance, stealth, range, payload, stability, and corrosion resistance, and at the same time, a reduction in lifetime costs. A comprehensive review of the potential use of composite materials for future vessels has been provided by Mouritz, Geller, Burchill, and Challis [1]. Practice shows that vessels fabricated from composites can have a greater survivability; however, composites materials are not typically used in isolation due to their insufficient stiffness and ductility compared to metallic materials. Thus, there has been growing interests in metal and composite combined structures. However, joints in composite structures are susceptible to failure when subjected to high rate loading from an impulsive

load source. Therefore, one major structural challenge is the design of metal-to-composite hybrid joints. Hybrid joints often entail geometry and material discontinuities; these can induce stiffness mismatch and cause local stress concentrations. Also, shock impedance mismatch caused by the different wave propagation characteristics in hybrid joints can be critical to the structural response under impulsive loads.

The behavior and ultimate load capacity of metal-to-composite hybrid joints fabricated with different joining methods under various loading conditions have been studied recently at ICL and USNA. Initial tensile test results of steel-to-vinyl ester glass reinforced polymers (GRP) double lap joints are presented in this paper, comparing joints with perforated steel plates with those manufactured with non-perforated steel plates and comparing dynamic strength with pseudo-static strength.

II. BACKGROUND

Applying perforations to the metallic part of hybrid joints was first considered by Unden and Ridder [2]. Perforations were first used to increase the cohesion between metal and composite adherends, thus improving the transfer of load between the metallic and composite parts. Additionally, perforations in the steel were believed to decrease the elastic mismatch between the stiff steel adherend and the more compliant composite adherend. Melograna and Grenestedt [3] and Cao and Grenestedt [4] further investigated and improved this joint design. Joints were found to have the highest strength when comprised of seven to nine rows of circular holes. The best performing perforated joints tested yielded 25-30% higher tension strength than their non-perforated counterparts, agreeing with Hart-Smith's [5] conclusion. He found that the hybrid joint's capacity can be increased when the joint is designed to reduce the stiffness imbalance. Finally, it should be noted that recent work has mainly focused pseudo-static testing of perforated joints.

III. EXPERIMENTATION

A. Design and Fabrication of Specimens

This research is an extension of work performed by Melograna and Grenestedt [3] in which double lap steel-to-vinyl ester GRP joints were tested statically. Several steel perforation geometries were examined including circular perforations with graduated diameters. Figures 1 and 2 show that the perforations near the tip of the steel plate have the largest diameter and the perforation diameter reduces as distance from the tip of the plate increases. The variation in diameter gradually increases the effective axial stiffness of the steel plate, reducing the effects of stiffness mismatch between the GRP and steel plate.

Fig.1. Perforation geometry

Fig. 2. Overall specimen geometry in mm used in this study

Melograna and Grenestedt's [3] strongest joint was the starting point for the joint design in this study; however, grade 304 stainless steel was used for this study. This steel is a thinner, lower strength steel compared to the steel used for Melograna and Grenestedt's joints. Thus to ensure that failure would occur in the joints themselves rather than in the steel plate beyond the joint, a shorter lap length was used here, 40mm rather than 50mm. Also the number of rows of perforations was reduced from nine to eight. Finally, the specimen geometry beyond the joint itself is dictated by the Impact Tension Adapter (ITA) loading device (see Figure 2).

Twenty two hybrid tension specimens were manufactured at USNA. A Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM) process was employed. In the region of the joint itself, the steel plate was grit blasted and degreased before fabrication. The perforations were formed using a water jet cutter. The water jet cutter was subsequently used to cut the individual specimens. As shown in Figure 3, the reinforcement

layout for the GRP portions of the specimens was four layers of tri-axial glass fiber reinforcement fabric, TTX1330 (+45°/0°/-45°). A layer of Fiber Glast Mat 251 continuous mat was placed at mid thickness between the upper and lower pairs of TTX1330 in order that the GRP thickness matched the steel plate thickness. In order to provide a sacrificial gripping surface, the GRP adherends were thickened beyond the test region by adding one more layer of TTX1330 to the top and bottom of the stack. The resin used was Dow Derakane 510A-40 vinyl ester. Finally, semi-circular pieces of single-sided self-adhesive polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) tape were applied to both sides of the steel plate prior to fabrication of half of the specimens to create intentional fabrication flaws (see Figure 4).

Fig. 3. GRP laminate layup

Fig. 4. Arrangement of flaw

B. Testing of Specimens

To determine both baseline strength and failure behavior against which the dynamically loaded specimens could be compared, five perforated and five non-perforated specimens were tested under pseudo-static tensile loading. For the pseudo-static tests, an Instron uni-axial twin screw test machine fitted with a 2580 series static load cell with a crosshead displacement rate of 1mm/min was used. In order to measure strain in the GRP plates, strain gauges were applied to the GRP portion of the static specimens beyond the joint

itself as shown in Figure 2. Measurement data was recorded from the load cell, crosshead displacement transducer, and the strain gauges.

Additionally six perforated and six non-perforated specimens were tested under dynamic tensile loading (impact velocity ≈ 4.1 m/s) in order to expose differences, in terms of tension strength and failure behavior. To generate the dynamic loading, an Instron Dynatup 9200 drop weight test rig was used. Using the ITA designed and manufactured at ICL, the impact load generated by the drop weight test rig is converted into a dynamic tension load (see Figure 5 for details). An impact energy of 45J was generated using a drop weight mass of 5.2kg. Strain gauges were applied to both the GRP and steel adherends as shown in Figure 2. An accelerometer was fixed to the upper surface of the bottom yoke of the ITA. Measurement data from the strain gauges, impact tup load cell and ITA accelerometer were recorded with a data acquisition rate of 10MHz during the testing.

Fig. 5. Impact Tension Adapter (ITA)

C. Experimental Results

The mean failure loads for both the static and dynamic testing are given in Table I. Figures 6 and 7 show typical load versus extension plots for both static and dynamic loading, respectively. In the static tests the extension is derived from the universal test machine, while for the dynamic loading the extension is calculated using data from the accelerometer which is mounted on the bottom yoke of the ITA.

When the joint is tested to failure, relatively clean debonding of the GRP from the surface of the steel plates was observed (see Figure 8). There are some remaining fibers bonded to the steel surface; however, these are most likely stitch yarns of the fabric and not the actual reinforcing fibers. Figure 9 shows gaps between the steel adhering perforations and resin; these gaps are present in all of the tested perforated joints. They indicate that the perforated steel adherends have undergone plastic deformation prior to joint failure.

TABLE I. PHYSICAL TEST RESULTS, MEAN FAILURE LOAD IN KN AND SPREAD OF RESULTS (%)

	Static		Dynamic	
	Mean	Spread (%)	Mean	Spread (%)
Perforated Joint No Flaw	10.8	($\pm 3\%$)	15.2	($\pm 15\%$)
Perforated Joint With Flaw	11.0	($\pm 5\%$)	14.9	($\pm 1\%$)
Non-perforated Joint No Flaw	4.4	($\pm 56\%$)	6.2	($\pm 2\%$)
Non-perforated Joint With Flaw	4.5	($\pm 32\%$)	6.6	($\pm 6\%$)

Fig. 6. Physical test load versus extension plots for static tests

Solid line for non-perforated joints, dashed line for perforated joints.

Fig. 7. Physical test load versus extension plots for dynamic tests

Solid line for non-perforated joints, dashed line for perforated joints.

Fig. 8. Steel plate from a tested specimen

Fig. 9. Plastic deformation in the perforated steel plate

A quantitative comparison with Melograna and Grenestedt's [3] results is not particularly meaningful due to differences in steel surface preparation, steel plate material, and steel plate thickness. However, results for the quasi-statically loaded joints are qualitatively in agreement with the previous results. The perforated joints had significantly higher tensile strengths compared to non-perforated joints. Additionally, an enhancement in strength for the perforated joints under dynamic loading was also found.

Perforated joints are approximately 2.4 times stronger than non-perforated joints for both static and dynamic loading. Low specification for the steel surface preparation contributes to the difference in strength. The enhancement under dynamic loading is slightly less; however, this difference is small compared to the spread in results data. It was expected that the strength enhancement under dynamic loading would be lower for the perforated joints due to the fact that plastic softening of the steel will occur at a higher stress as the loading rate increases. The stiffness mitigation effect of the perforations should tend to diminish at higher loading rates due to this stiffening of the steel.

In addition, intentional flaws were found to have a negligible effect on the strength of either type of joint under either type of loading. However, the small number of specimens and spread of results may be hiding any influence; this is particularly true for the non-perforated joints.

Finally a significant enhancement in tension strength under dynamic loading for both perforated and non-perforated

joints was found (see Table I). In the dynamic testing, strain rates of approximately 1.4 s^{-1} and 4.0 s^{-1} were generated for the steel adherend and GRP adherend, respectively. Based on data from the literature, we expect that the increase in tension modulus from these strain rates would be greater for the steel than for the GRP and, as mentioned earlier, an increase in steel stiffness should decrease the strength of the joint, due to an increase in the stiffness mismatch between the two materials. Therefore strain rate effects on the adherend materials are not likely to be the source of the increase in joint strength under dynamic loads. The more likely source appears to be an enhancement in the cohesive bond between the adherends. Unfortunately there appears to be little consensus in the literature regarding the effect of loading rate on either Mode I or Mode II cohesion for epoxy resins.

IV. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

For both perforated and non-perforated joints, Finite Element (FE) models were created using Abaqus 6.12. Each model is a 3D half model that takes advantage of the through thickness symmetry of the joint. Eight node linear brick (C3D8R) elements are used. Adherend bondline failure is modeled using cohesive surface interactions. In the case of the perforated joints, cohesive surface interaction is also used for the bond surfaces of the resin in the steel perforations. A Cohesive Zone Model (CZM), as indicated in Figure 10, defines the behavior of the cohesive surface. Unfortunately a literature search has not provided all of the parameters that are required for the CZM, so it has been necessary to make an initial estimate of suitable parameters and then to carry out a parametric study with the aim of calibrating the CZM model against the physical test data. The required parameters are:

- σ_n^{\max} , initiation stress in the normal direction
- τ_s^{\max} , τ_t^{\max} , initiation stress in the two orthogonal shear directions
- $K_{nn} = \frac{\sigma_n^{\max}}{u_n^0}$, stiffness in the normal direction
- $K_{tt} = \frac{\tau_t^{\max}}{u_t^0}$, stiffness in the shear direction
- G_{IC} & G_{IIC} , fracture energy in the normal and shear directions respectively

To determine an initial baseline estimate of these parameters for a GRP-to-resin, CZM data given by Zhou, Louca, and Saunders [6] and CVC Thermoset Specialities [7] have been used (see Table II). With regard to the bond between the GRP plate and the resin that fills the perforations in the steel plate, it should be noted that we are assuming that the behavior of this bond is matrix dominated, i.e. it is dominated by the GRP resin rather than the fibers. Therefore we assume it is valid to use fracture data derived from GRP specimens, i.e. a GRP-to-GRP interface, for the GRP-to-resin

interface in our FE models. In order to adjust these GRP-to-GRP parameters, a FE parametric study has been completed and is described below.

The FE models of the perforated and non-perforated joints have been used to carry out a parametric study on the CZM for both the GRP-to-steel bond and the GRP-to-resin bond. The perforated joints have two pairs of interface materials, i.e. GRP / steel and GRP / resin while the non-perforated joints only have one pair of interface materials at the bondline, i.e. GRP / steel. Therefore the non-perforated joint model has only a single set of CZM parameters that is required to model the bondline interface; thus the non-perforated joint model was the first type to be used in the parametric study. The following iteration methodology was used for the parametric study:

1. Carry out a displacement controlled explicit analysis in Abaqus using the CZM parameters given in Table II. Material stiffness and plasticity parameters were determined from physical coupon tests carried out at ICL.
2. Determine the tensile failure load of the joint for this CZM.
3. Apply a factor to the peak stress and fracture toughness parameters of the CZM in order to modify the strength of the CZM and thus modify the tensile failure load of the joint. A “similar triangles” approach was used when factoring the parameters. The same reduction factor was applied to both the peak stress and the fracture toughness parameter in order to define the adjusted CZM. See Figure 10 which shows the effect of applying factors of 0.65 and 0.30 to the CZM of Table II.
4. Repeat steps 1, 2 and 3 until a good match is achieved between the failure load of the model and the physical test failure load.

TABLE II. BASELINE INITIAL ESTIMATE OF CZM PARAMETERS [6,7]

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Initial stiffness Normal direction	K_{nn}	10,000	N/mm
Initial stiffness Shear direction 1 & 2	K_{ss}, K_{tt}	4,000	N/mm
Peak stress Normal direction	σ_n^{max}	9.0	N/mm ²
Peak stress Shear direction 1 & 2	$\tau_s^{max}, \tau_t^{max}$	31.4	N/mm ²
Fracture toughness Mode I	G_{Ic}	800	J/m ²
Fracture toughness Mode II	G_{IIc}	1600	J/m ²

Fig 10. Graphical representation of Cohesive Zone Models (CZM)

As previously mentioned, only grit blasting and degreasing of the steel plate bond surface of the joint specimens was performed. Thus, we would expect that the strength of the bond between the GRP and the steel plate will be significantly weaker than that of the GRP-to-resin bond represented by the baseline CZM of Table II. A parametric study using a FE model of the non-perforated joint shows that a factor of 0.30 needs to be applied to the baseline CZM in order to replicate the average failure load from the physical testing, see Figure 11. Since the FE model is a half model, the load of 2.2 kN from the analysis matches the average failure load of 4.4 kN from the testing.

Figure 11 shows the tension load versus time plot of the FE model of the non-perforated joint, the cohesive zone damage at the bondline, and the distribution of axial stress. The damage and stress images are taken just prior to failure of the joint as indicated by the vertical red bar on the load versus time plot. Further work with this FE model is ongoing.

A second study using a FE model of the perforated joint has been undertaken. In this case, the 0.3 x baseline CZM is applied to all of the GRP-to-steel interfaces at the bond line and the baseline CZM is initially applied to the GRP-to-resin interface, i.e. where the resin that penetrates the steel perforations is bonded to the inside face of the GRP lap. A similar iteration methodology to that described above was used with the perforated joint. Although in this case the CZM for the GRP-to-steel interface was not modified; only the CZM for the GRP-to-resin interface was modified. A factor of 2.25 to the baseline CZM was found to give good correlation of failure loads comparing the FE model and test results.

Fig. 11. Abaqua results for the non-perforated joint

a) Cohesive zone damage b) Axial stress

c) Load versus time plot

Selected frames from the perforated joint FEA along with the load versus time plot for the same analysis are shown in Figure 12. The frame images show the bondline surface of the GRP lap. The extent of CZM damage on the surface is represented by the color gradient; blue indicates 0% damage while red indicates 100% damage. The bond is at full stiffness while the damage is at 0% and has zero stiffness when the damage has reached 100%. As shown in Figure 12, the damage progresses as follows:

- Frame 2. The butt surface at the tip of the steel plate becomes de-bonded very early in the loading phase of the analysis.
- Frame 10. The shear surface of the steel plate gradually de-bonds from the face of the GRP while the shear surfaces of the resin in the perforations remains largely intact.
- Frame 95. At maximum load the shear surface of the steel plate has become fully de-bonded from the GRP and the resin in the top row of perforations (the smallest perforations) has almost fully de-bonded from the GRP.
- Frame 150. During final failure, de-bonding of the resin in the perforations has tended to progress from the top of the joint down towards the larger perforations at the bottom.

Fig. 12. Progression of failure in the perforated joint FE model

Finally Figure 13 shows selected frames from a High Speed Video (HSV) that was captured during a dynamic test of a perforated joint. These images are shown along with the GRP strain versus time plot from the same test. The frame images are in pairs; the left hand image in each pair shows the raw image from the HSV while the right hand image shows the same image with a high pass filter applied. The high pass filter helps to highlight the change in brightness in the image, accentuating the delaminated areas. The damage shown in Figure 13 progresses in a largely similar manner to that described above for the FE model. However, two significant differences are:

1. During final failure in the physical test, it appears that damage of the GRP-to-resin bond starts at the

bottom of the joint, i.e. at the larger perforations, rather than the smaller perforations.

- The bulk GRP material beyond the joint itself has started to delaminate.

Fig. 13. Progression of failure in a perforated joint

Most likely these two phenomena are connected. The current FE model does not permit delamination in the GRP material. This will need to be corrected in future models with the aim of mimicking the physical test behavior more closely.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Research into both static and dynamic tensile strength of perforated steel-to-GRP joints is on-going. Both physical testing and FE modeling is being carried out. To assess the effect of manufacturing flaws on joint strength, intentional flaws were incorporated into half of the joints, both perforated and non-perforated joints. A universal screw jack test machine has been used for the static testing. The ITA was used to transform the load from a drop weight impact rig into a tension load for the dynamic testing. The perforated joints had a similar tension strength enhancement under dynamic loads as they do under pseudo-static loads. Additionally, the dynamic strength is greater than the static strength of both perforated and non-perforated joints. Future work includes the investigation into the origin of the apparent increase in strength of the joints under dynamic loading. Mode II fracture toughness for GRP-GRP and GRP-steel interfaces at a range of loading rates will be studied along with FE modeling of the hybrid joints under dynamic tension loading.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the team at TSD, Project Support Branch, US Naval Academy under the guidance of Mr Doug Loup, Naval Surface Warfare Center Carderock Division for fabricating the specimens used in the experiments, Office of Naval Research for funding the project and Andy Pullen at Imperial College London for his assistance in the experimental work.

REFERENCES

- Mouritz, A.P., Geller, E., Burchill, P., and Challis, K., "Review of advanced composite structures for naval ships and submarines", *Composite Structures*, 53(1): pp. 21-42, 2001.
- Uden, H. and Ridder, S.-O., *Load-introducing armature as component part of a laminated structural element*, 1987.
- Melograna, J. D. and Grenestedt, J. L., "Improving joints between composites and steel using perforations", *Composites: Part A*, 33, pp. 1253-1261, 2002.
- Cao, J. and Grenestedt, J.L., *Design and testing of joints for composite sandwich/steel hybrid ship hulls*. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 35(9): p. 1091-1105, 2004.
- Hart-Smith, L.J., *Design of adhesively bonded joints*, in *Joining fibre-reinforced plastics*, F.L. Matthews, Editor. 1987, Elsevier Applied Science: Barking, Essex, England. p. 271 - 311, 1987.
- Zhou, D.W., Louca, L.A., and Saunders, M., *Numerical simulation of sandwich T-joints under dynamic loading*. *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 39(6): pp. 973-985, 2008.
- CVC Thermoset Specialties, *Fracture Toughness of Elastomer Modified E-glass Reinforced Vinyl Ester Composites*: Moorestown, New Jersey.